

**METHODS OF STUDYING THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF
MENTALLY WEAK STUDENTS OF Q HOME CLASS ON THE BASE OF
INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES**

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ABSTRACT

This in the article given technologies based on lower class mind weak students school to education spiritual and intellectual in terms of readiness experimental research to do methods cause passed. Mind weak students knowledge get activities learning during them to education more interest gain light up given.

KEYWORDS: *Speech, General Motor, Small Hand Motor Skills, Knowledge Activity, Analyzer, Mind Weakness, Anomaly, Behavior.*

INTRODUCTION

The level of pedagogical and psychological development of the child is studied when entering the educational institution. This makes it possible to identify the individual's strengths or congenital, acquired anomalies at an early age. Including the process of transition from a lower class to a higher class.

The purpose of the experimental study of the mental and intellectual readiness of the mentally retarded students for school education: to diagnose the level of pedagogical-psychological readiness of the mentally retarded students for education.

The correct use of methods of examination of students with mental retardation in the lower grades will determine their correct diagnosis. The program for correct diagnosis and correct analysis of students with mental retardation in grades 3-4 includes:

- Test is experience work right organization. The result analysis to do
- To the age looking speech development level
- Test is experience for selected methods right explain, they with in detail by introducing exit
- Children of activity features.
- Motivation.

Lower class mind weak students to education pedagogical - psychological preparation We are following in the inspection from the methods we used

The research experiment was conducted in three stages.

At the first stage, using biographical methods (reports of the psychological-medical-pedagogical commission and the study of children's personal affairs), the anamnestic data of children with intellectual disabilities were analyzed, the symptoms and characteristics of the disorder were determined. During the interview with the oligophrenopedagogue, educator and doctor, the behavior and development characteristics of the mentally retarded students of the lower class were clarified, the test subjects were observed (in the classroom, in play activities).

In the second stage, the level and characteristics of the formation of perceptive, mnemonic skills and thinking operations in children were studied using a set of diagnostic methods.

It should be noted that the total number of diagnostic tasks presented to students with mental retardation was about 30. In the process of presenting these tasks, it was necessary to distinguish the level of formation of perceptive and mnemonic skills and mental operations in a mentally retarded child, and the level of independence of the child in performing the experimental task.

To study general intellectual abilities, the methods presented in the works of SD Zabramnaya, VG Petrova, ON Usanova and others were used in their original and modified form. The modification of the methods was carried out by introducing a training phase into them, which involves the consistent provision of different doses and types of support to the test subject in order to determine the level of his learning ability. Three types of support were provided in the instructional phase: motivational, directional, and instructional. Stimulating support in case of low learning activity of a preschooler, guide - in the case of slow orientation in the task and deficiencies in action planning, teacher - in case of complete inability to perform at least some reasonable actions used. This type of support is not strictly defined and is provided depending on which component of the child's educational activity is lacking in solving a particular problem. Each of these types, in turn, could have subtypes that differ in the degree of influence on the child's functioning. These subtypes are fixed in the order in which they are presented to testers.

In the third stage, qualitative and statistical analysis of the research results, comparison of all the obtained data was carried out, conclusions were drawn about the development characteristics of the mentally retarded students of the lower class.

"Different in color lines and circles" methodology

SD Zabramnaya methodo ' has been changed is an option.

The goal is to sort objects by color mutually _ _ tie up ability learning, pedagogue naming through the color identify, adults indicated by k o ' of forms the color naming Research In this process we of perceptive abilities formation level to evaluate possibility giving develop an efficiency scale exit for the purpose of this task of execution quality degrees means separation we caught

The stimulus material is basic colors and has colors (yellow, fire color, red, purple, blue, green, brown, black, white) lines that are and circles with expressed. Inspection task consecutively to complicate implying three stage was held.

First stage students to the superimposed lines suitable coming in color circles they choose The goal is to sort objects by color visual respectively mutually tie up their ability one by one establish compliance ability to determine Instructions : " Lines suitable coming circles choose ".

Second stage to the testee that or this the color You will be asked to choose: "Me red the circle give" Give meako give" and etc. The goal- the concept of color impressive use in speech ability to determine

Third stage taught by the experimenter from the subject of the form the color naming is asked: "What color is this? What about this?" The goal is the concept of color impressive use in speech ability to determine

The results assessment:

I level - student circles and lines by color b mutually connect cannot, ko' instructions according to known in color show the circle can't, experimenter indicated by k o ' of the form the color ca n't name it (0 points).

II degree - some of the child colors t o ' grybinds , but activity During this time he did not steal to actions o ' tadi - colors confused sends (0 points).

III degree - some of the child match the colors connects (shows, names), but color was similar colors confused sends (0.5 points).

IV degree - the child is known in color objects completely right connects (shows, names) (1 point).

Work done each one stage separately is evaluated, according to points is summarized. All three of stage in sum the maximum number of points is 3 organize does Series relative to independence have, but they of activity step by step that it becomes complicated into itself takes and the only one the goal and research material with unite, this describes the method as holistic and taken in three series the results to generalize basis gives

"Subject images tables and their geometric forms " methodology

ON Usanova's has been changed is a methodology.

ON Usanova's mind weak of children form with movement to do ability to learn directed methodology of the child subject-practice activities activation mean holds Your child perception reach activity for was unusual geometric forms In addition to the methodology of ON Usanova, whose standards are used, we have two experimental the assignment work we went out , in them geometric forms of the student experience (circle, triangle, square and others) into account received without present will be done. We are this series initially to the child not so much It was n't complicated presented as a series we did, then while more difficult the task (third series) - ON Usanova geometric forms offer we did

Necessary equipment is an object images and their forms. First collection circle, square , triangle forms in to itself takes Second collection right rectangular, oval , trapezoidal shapes is expressed . Third collection ON Usanova methodology ng geometric includes forms.

Research in the process of the child forward geometric forms q o ' year gan and instruction offer qilingan: "To forms suitable coming pictures placing need. Then, gestures to the child using work independent respectively continue carry on offer done Serials consecutively present ethyl.

Teaching stage :a) gestures with along with the instruction is shown: "To the circle round in the form of putting bodies, square - square - shaped ones need , etc."; b) to the child task completion

enough arli that it is not about hint is given; c) experimenter to the image set the standard , then the examiner is invited to try these actions do it.

The results Assessment: Level II - the child is presented the instruction given understands, but forms according to the size arrange can't (0 points).

Level III - objects by the examinee known one according to order placed , but researcher according to what he gave not, for example, forms in order When asked to place, the child them decrease in order places (2 points).

Level IV - test assignment it is full of instructions suitable respectively performs (3 points).

Experience three collection The maximum score is 9. Help each one stage each one collection score on 0.5 to reduce it Research in the process of the examinee previous in the series received experience next of the series to the assignment transfer I think it's possible done Methodology this features all by testers in series received the results to generalize possibility gave.

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